

EFFECT OF ABIOTIC FACTORS ON INCIDENCE OF MAJOR INSECT PESTS OF MUSTARD (*BRASSICA* SP.) CROP

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ABSTRACT : An experiment was carried out to investigate the effect of abiotic factors on incidence of major insect pests of mustard during *rabi* 2016-17 and 2017-18 at Crop Research Centre of SVPUA & T, Meerut (UP). The results showed that the incidence of mustard aphid, painted bug and cabbage butterfly started during 3rd, 6th and 4th standard week, and attained their peaks during 8th, 10th and 9th standard week, respectively during *rabi* 2016-17. However, in *rabi* 2017-18 the incidence of mustard aphid and Cabbage butterfly started during 4th while the incidence of painted bug started during 5th standard week and attained their peaks during 9th and 11th standard week respectively. Correlation studies revealed that aphid population showed a non-significant positive correlation with morning relative humidity ($r = 0.29$) and non-significant negative correlation with maximum temperature ($r = -0.25$), minimum temperature ($r = -0.37$), evening relative humidity ($r = -0.01$) and rainfall ($r = -0.13$), while painted bug showed significant positive correlation with morning relative humidity ($r = 0.54$) and rainfall ($r = 0.53$) and non-significant negative correlation with maximum temperature ($r = -0.04$) and minimum temperature ($r = -0.16$) however cabbage butterfly showed non-significant positive correlation with maximum temperature ($r = 0.09$) and morning and evening relative humidity ($r = 0.12$) and ($r = 0.01$) and a non-significant negative correlation with minimum temperature ($r = -0.25$) and rainfall ($r = -0.13$), respectively during *rabi* 2016-17. However, during *rabi* 2017-18 aphid population indicated non-significant positive correlation with rainfall ($r = 0.22$) and non-significant negative correlation with maximum temperature ($r = -0.11$), minimum temperature ($r = -0.28$), morning relative humidity ($r = -0.46$) and evening relative humidity ($r = -0.26$) and painted bug population indicated positive correlation with maximum temperature ($r = 0.48$) and minimum temperature ($r = 0.27$) and a significant negative correlation with morning humidity ($r = -0.50$) and a non-significant negative correlation with evening relative humidity ($r = -0.21$) and rainfall ($r = -0.36$), while the larval population of cabbage butterfly indicated non-significant positive correlation with maximum temperature ($r = 0.25$) and morning and evening relative humidity ($r = 0.44$) and ($r = 0.39$), and a non-significant negative correlation with minimum temperature ($r = -0.43$), and rainfall ($r = -0.28$).

Key words : Mustard aphid, painted bug, cabbage butterfly and incidence.

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INTRODUCTION

Rapeseed-mustard (*Brassica* sp.) is a major group of oilseed crop of the world being grown in 53 countries across the six continents. India contributes 28.3% in world acreage and 19.8% in world production. India produces around 6.7 million tonnes of mustard next to China (11-12 million tonnes) and Europe (10-13 million tonnes) with significant contribution in world rapeseed-mustard industry. Mustard (*Brassica juncea* Coss) is grown mainly for its seeds, which yield good quality of edible oil to the extent of 30 to 48%. In India mustard is cultivated over an area of 6.65 million hectare with production of 7.10 million tonnes of seed. The average yield of mustard

in country is 1069 kg/ha (Anonymous, 2017).

Among the several insects infesting the mustard, mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.) is the most serious insect-pest of rapeseed-mustard. It may cause a yield losses ranging from 35.4 to 96% in favourable conditions and can reduce 5-6% oil content (Sahoo, 2012).

Painted bug (*Bagrada hilaris* (Burmeister)) is another major insect of mustard in western Uttar Pradesh (Singh, 2008). It is very serious insect of rapeseed mustard and found active during seedling stage (October-November) and at harvest stage (March-April) (Palumbo and Natwick, 2010). Both nymphs and adults suck cell